

Synthesis of some Benzoxazin-4-one Derivatives and Study of their Reaction with Nucleophilic Reagents

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Manuscript received 17 July 1991, revised 12 March 1992, accepted 16 July 1992

In view of the important biological activities displayed by coumarins and 3,1-benzoxazin-4-one¹⁻⁴, it was considered worthwhile to prepare compounds having both of these moieties. It was also our interest to study the behaviour of such compounds toward different nucleophilic reagents.

Treatment of coumarin-3-carbonyl chloride (1) with anthranilic acid derivatives in dry pyridine afforded the amides (2a-c) which on cyclisation with acetic anhydride gave the 2-(coumarin-3-yl)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-ones (3a-c). Aminolysis of 3a, b with boiling ethanolic ammonia gave the 2-(coumarin-3-yl)-4-3H-quinazolones (4a, b). The formation of 4a, b takes place through rapid fission of the benzoxazine ring with ethanolic ammonia followed by ring closure under the reaction conditions.

Aminolysis of 3b with primary amines in boiling alcohol was successful and 5a-c were obtained as products. Alcoholysis of 3a, c with boiling alcohol gave the corresponding coumarin-3-N-[2-alkoxy-carbonylaryl]carboxamides (6a-g).

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. Elemental analysis were carried out in the microanalytical laboratories of the Faculty of Science, Cairo University. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a Shimadzu IR 440 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer, high field ¹H nmr (400 MHz) spectra on a

Burker WM 400 spectrometer and mass spectra on a Varian MAT 711 spectrometer (70 eV).

Condensation of coumarin-3-carbonylchloride (1) with anthranilic acids: To a solution of the requisite anthranilic acid (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (20 ml), coumarin-3-carbonyl chloride (1) was added portionwise during ca 30 min. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and then decomposed with ice-cold dilute HCl. The product obtained was crystallised from appropriate solvent to give 2a-c (Table 1): ν_{\max} 1 683, 1 717 (CO) and 3 500-2 500 cm^{-1} (OH and NH); 2c δ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) 7.45-7.71 (4H, m, ArH), 8.23 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_A), 8.34 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_B) and 8.75 (1H, s, =CH-); 2b m/z 387 (M^+) 389 ($M^+ + 2$), 173 (100%), 371, 369, 345, 343, 262, 217, 215, 199, 197, 170, 148, 145, 120, 116, 101, 91, 90, 89, 78, 75, 64, 62, 52 and 51; mass spectrum of 2c did not exhibit molecular ion peak, the other important peaks were observed at m/z 451 ($M+4\cdot H_2O$), 449 ($M+2\cdot H_2O$), 447 ($M-H_2O$) and the base peak at m/z 173 (100%).

2-(Coumarin-3-yl)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (3a-c): A mixture of 2 (2 g) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water (200 ml). The residue was washed several times with cold water and recrystallised from proper solvent to give 3a-c (Table 1): ν_{\max} 1 758-1 729 cm^{-1} (CO); 3b δ 7.36-7.72 (4H, m, ArH), 7.7 (1H, d, J_1 8 Hz, H_A),

NOTES

- a ; $X_1 = X_2 = H$
- b ; $X_1 = H, X_2 = Br$
- c ; $X_1 = X_2 = Br$

Aminolysis

Ammonolysis

(3b)

(3a,b)

Alcoholysis
(3a,c)

- a ; $R = CH_2Ph$
- b ; $R = C_6H_5$
- c ; $R = C_6H_4OCH_3-P$

- a ; $R = CH_3, X_1 = X_2 = H$
- b ; $R = CH_2CH_3, X_1 = X_2 = H$
- c ; $R = n-Butyl, X_1 = X_2 = H$
- d ; $R = CH_3, X_1 = H, X_2 = Br$
- e ; $R = CH_2CH_3, X_1 = H, X_2 = Br$
- f ; $R = n-Butyl, X_1 = H, X_2 = Br$
- g ; $R = n-Butyl, X_1 = X_2 = Br$

- a ; $X = H$
- b ; $X = Br$

Scheme 1

7.96 (1H, dd, J_1 8 Hz, J_2 2 Hz, H_B), 8.55 (1H, d, J_1 2 Hz, H_X) and 8.72 (1H, s, =CH—); 3c δ 7.35–7.72 (4H, m, ArH), 8.21 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_A), 8.31 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_B) and 8.74 (1H, s, =CH—).

3-(Coumarin-3-yl)-4-3H-quinazoline (4a, b): A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and NH_4OH (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h in ethanol. The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent to give 4a (Table 1): ν_{max} 1 717 (CO), 3 125 and 3 292 cm^{-1} (NH and OH enolic); m/z (M^+) 290, 173 (100%) (base peak), 264, 145, 119, 101, 89, 75 and 93.

Aminolysis of 3b: A solution of 3b (0.01 mol) and benzylamine, aniline or *p*-anisidine (0.02 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from suitable solvent to give 5a–c (Table 1): ν_{max} 1 725–1 667 (CO) and 3 540–3 208 cm^{-1} (NH); 5b δ 7.36–7.73

(9H, m, ArH), 7.95 (1H, dd, J_1 8.5 and J_2 2.5 Hz, H_B), 8.38 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H_X), 8.7 (1H, d, J_1 8.5 Hz, H_A) and 8.72 (1H, s, H_A).

Alcoholysis of 3a–c: Compounds 3a–c (0.2 g) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (methanol, ethanol or *n*-butanol; 10 ml) and the solutions refluxed for ~2 h. On cooling the solid that separated out, was crystallised from proper solvent to give 6a–g (Table 1): ν_{max} 1 746 (CO) and 3 208 cm^{-1} (NH); 4e δ 1.43 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 4.48 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 7.37–7.74 (5H, m, ArH), 7.95 (1H, dd, J 7 and 2 Hz, H_B), 8.38 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_X), 8.71 (1H, s, H_A) and 8.91 (1H, s, =CH—); 6f δ 1.02 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, CH_3), 1.50 (2H, sextet, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 1.81 (2H, pentet, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 4.41 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, CH_2), 7.35–7.36 (5H, m, ArH, H_A), 8.19 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_X), 8.49 (1H, hump, NH), 8.74 (1H, dd, J 6 and 1 Hz, H_B) and 8.93 (1H, s, =CH); 4g δ 0.98 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.47 (2H, sextet, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 1.78 (2H, pentet, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 4.41 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 7.35–7.73 (5H, m, ArH, H_A), 8.17 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H_B), 8.44 (1H, hump, NH) and 8.94 (1H, s, =HC); 6d m/z 401 (M^+), 403 ($M+2$), 173 (100%) (base peak), 371, 369, 342, 329, 327, 299, 262, 226, 224, 206, 204, 190, 145, 101, 89, 75, 69, 63, 58 and 55; 6e m/z 415 (M^+), 417 ($M+2$), 173 (100%) (base peak), 403, 401, 371, 369, 344, 342, 315, 313, 299, 262, 234, 226, 224, 190, 145, 101, 89, 75, 69, 63, 57 and 55.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–4*

Compd. no.	M. p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	279 ^a	80	$C_{17}H_{11}NO_5$
b	292 ^a	85	$C_{17}H_{10}BrNO_5$
c	260 ^b	85	$C_{17}H_9BrNO_5$
3a	197 ^c	75	$C_{17}H_9NO_4$
b	255 ^c	80	$C_{17}H_8BrNO_4$
c	215 ^c	82	$C_{17}H_7Br_2NO_4$
4a	243 ^b	80	$C_{17}H_{10}N_2O_3$
b	275 ^d	84	$C_{17}H_9BrN_2O_3$
5a	280 ^e	65	$C_{24}H_{17}BrN_2O_4$
b	241 ^d	71	$C_{23}H_{16}BrN_2O_4$
c	242 ^c	73	$C_{24}H_{17}BrN_2O_4$
6a	180 ^f	65	$C_{18}H_{13}NO_5$
b	258 ^b	70	$C_{18}H_{12}NO_5$
c	191 ^g	65	$C_{21}H_{19}NO_5$
d	275 ^f	68	$C_{18}H_{12}BrNO_5$
e	185 ^b	69	$C_{18}H_{11}BrNO_5$
f	178 ^g	64	$C_{21}H_{18}BrNO_5$
g	179 ^g	72	$C_{21}H_{19}NO_5$

*C, H and N analyses found satisfactory. **Solvent for crystallisation: ^aAcOH, ^bEtOH, ^c C_6H_6 , ^dxylene, ^edioxan, ^fMeOH, ^g*sn*-BuOH.

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